

GREI

Generalist Repository Ecosystem Initiative

Harvard Dataverse Repository Use Cases

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As an NIH-funded researcher, I want to use the Harvard Dataverse Repository to share my data, so that I can comply with my data management and sharing plan and the conditions of my grant.

This use case highlights ways research teams can leverage generalist repositories to share project data.

Dataset title

HemOnc ontology
<https://doi.org/10.7910/DV/N/FPO4HB>

Investigators and affiliations

Jeremy Warner

- HemOnc.org LLC
- Brown University
- Lifespan Cancer Institute

Data type

Ontology

Use case date

February 2, 2023

Use case contact

Julian Gautier
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Background

Jeremy Warner is co-founder of HemOnc.org LLC and has led the development and publication of the HemOnc knowledge base at HemOnc.org since it started in 2011.

[HemOnc.org](#) is hosted on a wiki, where healthcare professionals browse and contribute data for describing chemotherapy drugs and regimens. The knowledge base started as a volunteer effort before Jeremy secured NIH grants to maintain and expand it. A large subset of the knowledge base is used to create an ontology called HemOnc, expressed in standard formats (the Web Ontology Language and the Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership common data model) so that other systems can use it, such as [the ATHENA – OHDSI Vocabulary Repository](#).

Healthcare professionals use the ontology to describe clinical trials, ultimately enhancing the discoverability of clinical trials data and improving researchers' understanding of the impacts of cancer treatments.

Use case

In 2021, Jeremy and his group wanted to make the data easier to cite, preserve and track as it evolved. He remembered using the Harvard Dataverse Repository the previous year to fulfill a journal's data sharing requirements and decided to use the repository again, publishing [a dataset in the Harvard Dataverse Repository](#) and updating it four or more times a year with major versions of the ontology.

He likes that the repository makes it simple to get a persistent identifier for the dataset and how the repository's [guestbook feature](#) lets him track who accesses the data. He also appreciates that the [repository's APIs](#) allow others to "subscribe" to the data, automating regular updates into their workflows and systems.

GREI Use Cases are supported by the National Institutes of Health (NIH) Office of Data Science Strategy/ Office of the NIH Director pursuant to OTA-21-009, "Generalist Repository Ecosystem Initiative (GREI)". NIH Image Gallery. GDF10 protein forms new brain cell connections (<https://www.flickr.com/photos/nihgov/22798807131/>). Courtesy of S. Thomas Carmichael, MD, PhD, David Geffen School of Medicine at the University of California Los Angeles. NIH funding: National Institute of Neurological Disorders and Stroke (NINDS). More information at <https://www.nih.gov/news-events/news-releases/scientists-identify-main-component-brain-repair-after-stroke>

As a researcher, I want to **FIND** research data of interest in the Harvard Dataverse Repository so that I can validate findings, reuse data, and build on work within my discipline.

This fictitious use case highlights ways researchers can leverage generalist repositories to find datasets for reuse.

Dataset title

Attitudes in Pakistan towards COVID-19 infection and prevention

Investigators and affiliations

Inaya Tauqir

Data type

Surveys and interviews

Use case date

February 20, 2023

Use case contact

Julian Gautier
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Background

Inaya Tauqir is studying what people living in Pakistan and surrounding countries think about COVID-19 infection and prevention.

While thinking about how to conduct the research, she searches online for what others have published about this topic. One of the articles she finds was published in F1000 Research.

Use case

The article's data availability statement points to a dataset in the Harvard Dataverse Repository, but she can't access the data because the files are restricted and the owners aren't replying to her emails. So she looks for other data in the repository, typing *covid AND attitudes* in the search box and scanning the first page of results.

Many of the datasets look helpful, but there are over 8 pages of results. To manage the search, Inaya sorts the results by date to start with the most recently published data. And to remove data that might be inaccessible, she uses the "Access" filter to see only datasets with "Public" files.

As she reviews the dataset's descriptions and files, she saves the citation files of several datasets into her Endnote account so she can look at the datasets more closely later and easily cite the datasets she uses.

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As an institution, I want to **REPORT** on all datasets from my institution in the Harvard Dataverse Repository, so that I can ensure compliance of research data sharing and management plan commitments by our researchers.

This fictitious use case highlights ways administrators can leverage generalist repositories to track and report data sharing at an organizational level.

Use case date

February 2, 2023

Use case contact

Julian Gautier
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Background

The scholarly repository librarian at a Carnegie R2 university helps track the outputs of the research activities that the university funds, including research data. Each academic quarter, the librarian prepares a report of the data published by the university's affiliates and submits the report to the university's Data Services Task Force. Then the university's Sponsored Programs Office, another member of the task force, uses the report to determine which funded research has complied with data sharing requirements and where that data is published.

The university encourages affiliates to use its own research data repository, but the librarian knows that affiliates also publish research data elsewhere. So he maintains a list of those places and procedures for finding the affiliate data they hold. The Harvard Dataverse Repository is one of those places.

Use case

To get a sense of the amount of data that university affiliates have published in the Harvard Dataverse, the librarian uses the [repository's advanced search](#) page to find datasets where the data depositor entered the university's name in the dataset's "Author Affiliation" metadata field, adjusting the search to account for popular spellings and abbreviations of the university's name, until he's confident that the search query returns most of the data that the university's affiliates have published in the repository.

To automate and streamline the discovery of this research data, the librarian works with Harvard Dataverse staff to [create an OAI-PMH set](#) that contains the results of his search queries. This lets him set up a harvesting job, where each week the university's repository imports the metadata of the datasets in the Harvard Dataverse. This way, the librarian needs to check only the university's repository to find data that affiliates have published in the Harvard Dataverse.

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As a funder from a specific NIH institute or in general, I want to find datasets we have funded in the Harvard Dataverse Repository, so that I can REPORT on compliance with policies, and TRACK impact of research funding and usage of data.

This fictitious use case highlights ways funders can leverage generalist repositories to track compliance with data sharing policies and understand data reuse.

Use case date

February 2, 2023

Use case contact

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Background

A Health Scientist Administrator at the NIH's Office of Data Sharing needs to report on the published data that's been created during research funded by a particular grant. While reviewing a research article published by one of the principle investigators funded by the grant, the administrator follows a citation to one of the PI's datasets in the Harvard Dataverse Repository and searches the repository to see if it contains more data associated with the grant.

Use case

To find other data in the repository created during research funded by the grant, the administrator pastes the grant number into the repository's search box. That search returns five datasets. She clicks on some of the datasets to see how the data is related to the grant and sees the PI's name listed as an author for some of the datasets.

When the administrator is certain that she's found all data created during the grant-funded research, she lists each DOI in the report.

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As an institution, I use Harvard Dataverse as my institutional data repository infrastructure to provide my institution's researchers a place to deposit and share their research outputs, report on its aggregate usage, and connect those outputs via APIs to other systems.

This hypothetical use case highlights how institutions benefit by using Harvard Dataverse as their institutional data repository.

Use case date

March 15, 2024

Use case contact

Gustavo Durand
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Background

A research university wants to provide a place where their researchers can preserve and share their data. However they do not have the technical staff and infrastructure to stand up their own repository.

The researchers at the university require a repository that supports the FAIR principles. They would like to empower the consumers of their research outputs to further explore and visualize the data. Additionally, they would like to be able to login through their University SSO.

The university needs the ability to preserve research outputs and control who can deposit and access data in the IR. They would also like to connect to tools that can assist in curating the metadata and enabling large data uploads. Additionally, they want to provide usage metrics, such as the number of citations and downloads.

Use case

In order to satisfy the requirements of the researchers and the university, the university opts to create a dataverse collection hierarchy at Harvard Dataverse.

Harvard Dataverse plays a crucial infrastructure role by offering a data sharing solution that does not require local technology resources. It manages integration with DataCite to register DOIs for datasets and files, maintains authentication through the institution's SSO service, provides curation services and support for big data, and allows IR researchers to customize their collection pages. Furthermore, it ensures the quality and preservation of data, code, and metadata published in the IR and tracks data usage.

Via Harvard Dataverse's robust permission system, the university can control who has access to deposit in which subcollections and who can access which research objects (or allow the researchers to determine that access).

Harvard Dataverse also provides researchers built in connections to several other tools - from Turbo Curator from ICPSR to assist in AI powered data curation to Data Explorer from Borealis in order to better understand the data, among an ever growing inventory of external tools.

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As a researcher, I want to use the Harvard Dataverse Repository to share Big Data whose volume, variety, velocity, or veracity requires special infrastructure functionality or handling

This use case highlights ways generalist repositories support Big Data via specialized functionality for large and complex dataset

Dataset Title:

DrivAerNet++: Pressure

Investigators and affiliations:

Elrefaie, Mohamed (MIT); Ahmed, Faez (MIT); Dai, Angela (TUM); Morar, Florin (BETA CAE SYSTEMS USA)

Date:

November, 2024

Data type:

Visualization Toolkit (VTK)

Citations:

Elrefaie, Mohamed; Morar, Florin; Dai, Angela; Ahmed, Faez, 2024, "DrivAerNet++: Wall Shear Stress", <https://doi.org/10.7910/DV N/PCZYL4>, Harvard Dataverse, V1

Use Case Date:

2025-01-14

Use case Contact:

support@dataverse.harvard.edu

Background:

Researchers at Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT), the Technical University of Munich (TUM), BETA CAE Systems, and BikeCAD collaborated on a project producing four datasets, each with over 8,000 files each, totalling 16 T of data. They packaged the individual files in zip files to support easier downloading for data reusers. Then, they uploaded them to Harvard Dataverse Repository. The project is completed, the datasets will not be versioned, and the collection will not grow.

The data files themselves are stored on tape resources at the Northeast Storage Exchange (NESE). Datasets are downloaded using the Globus protocol and app.

Screenshots of the file landing page for one of the project's datasets. Note the zip files available for download and the icon indicating the files are stored on NESE tape resources.

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